

LAUNCHING WELLCOME'S INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH CULTURE COMMUNITY

Authors

Sonya Towers

Rosalind Attenborough

Faith Uwadiae

Furaha Asani

Tony Bhajam

Roseanna Dias

Executive Summary

At Wellcome, we believe that excellent research happens in environments where people from all backgrounds are treated with respect, supported and enabled to thrive. As part of our ongoing commitment to encouraging positive and inclusive research cultures, we invited 42 organisations based in the UK and Republic of Ireland to apply for [Institutional Funding for Research Culture \(IFRC\)](#) to advance their research cultures through ambitious projects of up to £1 million each. The funding was allocated to 23 organisations through partial randomisation: the principles and process behind IFRC are described in more detail [here](#).

With the investment of significant funds into research culture through IFRC, and extensive collective time and effort across organisations, a new opportunity opened up for sector-level learning about “what works” to create positive change in institutional research cultures. Just as importantly, these lessons could be about what does not work, what may be generalisable or scalable, and how context interacts with change initiatives. These lessons will add to a growing body of evidence about research culture challenges and research culture change initiatives.

To make the most of this shared opportunity, Wellcome has convened an Institutional Research Culture Community (IRCC) that brings together all IFRC applicants, regardless of whether they received funding. We hope that this community of practice will enable:

- Shared learning on how to improve cultures across the research sector.
- Cross-institutional support and collaboration between research culture projects, including through identification of shared goals and themes.
- Relationship-building between teams and individuals at different institutions.
- Building momentum and harnessing collective energy for sector-wide change.
- Growing a robust and open evidence base to support research culture change beyond this IRCC.

On 6th June 2024, Wellcome hosted the IRCC kick-off event, welcoming 176 in-person attendees and 110 online participants from 41 institutional teams (all 42 teams have opted to join the community). The event featured lightning talks around the community's key focus areas: Collaboration, Leadership, Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI), Responsible Research Practices, Career Development, and Evaluation. These presentations were followed by facilitated discussions on topics of shared interest within the community.

The event successfully initiated cross-institutional dialogues and collaborations, with many participants planning further interactions and applying shared insights to their work. Looking forward, the IRCC will continue to convene over the next two years, with a series of events and targeted gatherings supported by an embedded social research team, [Studio Susegad](#). The focus will be on shared learning and implementing meaningful change within the academic research landscape.

This report shares our aims and process for convening IRCC, what took place at the event, and our hopes for the next stages of this community, including sharing with the wider research sector.

Introduction

At Wellcome, we strive to support the people and communities working in research. We believe human working environments are the foundation of discovery, breakthroughs, and impact on urgent health challenges. This means that the best research happens when the people doing it and the communities involved are diverse, supported, and thriving.

There are systemic challenges that can make research a difficult, inequitable place to work, collaborate, or pursue a career. Although many people experience great joy and fulfilment in research environments, bad experiences are common, and too many people, often from underrepresented groups, are pushed out. Wellcome played a key role in acknowledging this reality with a campaign, [Reimagine Research](#), which included the largest-ever survey into experiences of research culture*.

In response to the insights from this campaign, Wellcome established the [Institutional Fund for Research Culture \(IFRC\)](#). The objective of this funding call was to provide up to £1 million to enable institutions to experiment with and develop initiatives that could lead to valuable and innovative understandings of how to foster positive and inclusive research environments. This call was open to 42 organisations, as listed in the appendix, which were selected based on having received at least 10 grants from Wellcome in the previous five years (2018-2023), a track record that positioned them ideally to trial innovative models to improve the research cultures for researchers funded by Wellcome.

Given the complexities in evaluating the broad range of topics and ideas to advance positive research cultures, we implemented partial randomisation in the distribution of funding. This approach was used to promote a fair and unbiased allocation process. 23 organisations were funded through this call. The names and project abstracts of these funded organisations are available on [Wellcome's website](#). Further details about the IFRC and the randomisation process are available in our [publication](#).

All the IRCC teams are addressing a diverse array of challenges within their research cultures, with ambitious plans for transformative change. Examples of these initiatives include fostering an anti-ableist research environment, enhancing career pathways for technicians, and encouraging collaborative, team-oriented science. The projects align with several key themes: 40% focus on Collaboration, 27% on Leadership, and 21% on Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI). Additionally, smaller portions of projects concentrate on Responsible Research Practices (7%), Career Development (3%), and Evaluation (3%). Further details regarding these key issues and the strategies teams are employing to address them are presented in the lightning talk section.

*The Royal Society defines research cultures as encompassing the behaviours, values, expectations, attitudes, and norms of our research communities. It influences researchers' career paths and determines the way that research is conducted and communicated.

Why Convene an Institutional Research Culture Community?

To make the most of this opportunity, Wellcome has established the Institutional Research Culture Community (IRCC), which will operate for at least two years, aligning with the IFRC funding period. This community brings together all IFRC applicants—regardless of funding status—to foster connections, offer mutual support, and share insights on enhancing institutional research cultures. We believe it is important to include unfunded groups in this initiative, acknowledging the valuable work all applicant organisations are undertaking to enhance their research cultures.

This unique community comprises individuals at various career stages and roles, including HR, research support staff, and technicians, both seasoned and new to the research culture space. Building on the foundation provided by our IFRC funding scheme and Wellcome's strategic position within the sector, the IRCC aims to leverage our resources, values, and influence to drive essential change in the academic research landscape, fostering more positive and inclusive environments for research communities to thrive.

We convened a community for several key reasons:

- **Supporting ambitious projects and learning from a new funding scheme:** The IFRC scheme is a new approach for Wellcome and provides significant institutional funding to support large-scale, higher-risk (with a high potential reward) ambitious research culture projects. By forming a community, project teams can receive cohort support and facilitate learning about the transformative impact of funding on research culture.
- **Developing new and robust research culture knowledge:** IFRC grants aim to generate significant, widely applicable knowledge on improving institutional research cultures. Each project includes an embedded evaluation component, which was a crucial aspect of the scheme's assessment criteria. Currently, there is a recognised knowledge gap in conducting robust evaluations of research culture projects, as highlighted by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) [Research Culture initiatives report](#). IFRC projects have the potential to grow an evidence base for the wider sector in this area.
- **Fostering collaboration and sector-wide change:** The IRCC encourages a collaborative space for exchanging knowledge, best practices, and lived experience of enacting research culture change. We hope that coming together as a community allows synergies between projects to be identified early on, potentially leading to coordinated or collaborative action between institutions that make the most of the resources and momentum provided by the IFRC scheme.
- **Sharing the benefits:** IFRC was a closed call targeting research institutions best placed to trial approaches to improving the research cultures of Wellcome-funded researchers. Recognising that both funded and non-funded teams are working on a range of important research culture projects, all teams were invited to join the community. The community presents an opportunity to exchange knowledge and provide support beyond the organisations Wellcome was able to directly support.

How We Convened this Community

We wanted a wide range of people in the teams applying to IFRC to feel that this community could be theirs and to make it useful for a range of needs. To achieve this, we embarked on an engaged community-convening process. Eight months prior to the kick-off event, we extended initial community invitations to representatives of institutional teams, having already highlighted community participation as a key aspect of the IFRC scheme in the application process. We set out the benefits we hoped would come from joining the community, and most importantly we asked: What would you want or need from this community? And what can you bring? These questions and others were in a survey, and we also invited representatives from each institution to have a short conversation with us.

41 teams completed our survey, and 29 teams (a mix of both funded and non-funded) opted to have a follow-up video call with us. We worked to connect with these teams, learn what they were excited about, and hear any concerns or fears they expressed. Every conversation was different, with common themes, and we came out of this process vastly more informed about what kind of community we could and should convene. We found that most respondents wanted to use the community to form new connections, particularly those outside the key existing research culture networks. Additionally, there was a widespread desire to build an evidence base on what works, what does not, why, and in what context. Teams were also keen to map commonalities and divergences across projects and institutions to identify where groups could work together and learn from one another. There was also a hope that the community could harness collective momentum to push for sector-wide change, moving beyond research culture “talk” into action. All the invaluable insight garnered from our extensive conversations informed the subsequent steps we took in designing the community kick-off event and shaping the future direction of the community.

The kick-off event: 6th June 2024

Guided by the community's suggestions and the expertise of event facilitators from the [Centre for Facilitation](#), we designed the day's schedule to begin with parallel three-minute lightning talk sessions and incorporated ample opportunities for networking throughout. The day concluded with facilitated discussions covering a wide range of research culture themes. These elements were designed to address three priorities for the kick-off event identified by institutional teams:

- Gaining insights into research culture projects and initiatives at other institutions.
- Networking and relationship-building as a foundation for further conversations.
- Engaging in focused, action-oriented conversations within research culture themes.

We carefully balanced these priorities, acknowledging that many community members were meeting for the first time, while also striving to initiate or continue meaningful discussions.

some, this community may not feel entirely "new," while for others, it provides a new opportunity to engage with research culture initiatives.

- **Promoting a Positive Culture:** We emphasised that, as a community, we are part of the context we seek to improve and are not immune from negative behavioural and cultural patterns in research cultures. Attendees were encouraged to be mindful of their behaviours and to support others.
- **Equal Welcome for All Attendees:** We ensured an inclusive welcome for both in-person and online participants, a commitment reinforced by our facilitators throughout the day.

We also sought to welcome the community in non-hierarchical ways, such as name tags without titles, in line with a suggestion from the community to avoid distinguishing between attendees based on perceived academic rank.

Themed Lightning Talks

The series of parallel three-minute lightning talks provided a platform for inter-team knowledge exchange about initiatives to enhance research culture. Institutional teams were invited to present, regardless of their funding status through IFRC. We provided the prompt “one challenge, one hope, one how”, and teams responded with concise, targeted presentations articulating institutional challenges within their research cultures, visions for future progress, and strategic plans for tackling these issues. [Scriberia](#) captured the key points from each session through illustrations. The talks were organised around six pivotal themes: Leadership; Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI); Career Development; Responsible Research Practice; Evaluation; and Collaboration.

During discussions centered on **Leadership**, there was a shared understanding of the challenges posed by overly hierarchical and inefficient approaches to institutional leadership. Participants highlighted a notable lack of diversity among leadership and senior roles. The attendees considered various strategies to diversify and improve leadership, including the implementation of leadership training programs aimed at equipping current and aspiring leaders with the skills necessary for fostering inclusive research environments. Teams emphasised the importance of recognising and cultivating essential leadership qualities, advocating for practices that promote and reward desired leadership behaviours. Additionally, the importance of critiquing and improving university research governance methods was a significant topic of discussion.

The concept of **EDI** was interwoven throughout the conversations in all sessions, with numerous participants speaking out about the necessity of enhancing equity and diverse representation within academia. Efforts to dismantle barriers to progression, particularly for those from marginalised groups and/or with caregiving responsibilities, were highlighted throughout the day. Teams strongly recognised the importance of employing approaches from both ends of the spectrum, top-down and bottom-up, to foster improvements in EDI. Conversations also revolved around improving access and support for researchers from underrepresented backgrounds, and the importance of monitoring grant success rates and promotions through an EDI lens. There was also discussion about how to nurture inclusive research cultures, including the importance of belonging, the impact of research environments on mental well-being, and the importance of supporting the inclusion of people living with a disability in the academic system.

Career development was another area of significant focus, with several teams highlighting the challenges associated with unstable contracts and the importance of moving towards more secure and permanent employment models. Teams discussed improving career advancement opportunities for technical staff through learning programs and leadership opportunities, and the concept of embedding 'roving researchers' was discussed as a means of bolstering support for staff during periods such as parental or medical leave. Discussions affirmed the value of recognising and destigmatising career trajectories that lead outside of academia and the pertinent role of mentorship for career development.

Several teams expressed the importance of championing **responsible research practices** through various approaches, including the promotion of equitable partnerships, through new models for team structures and team management, improving the sustainability of research practices, the incorporation of community involvement, and the implementation of thorough evaluation. Discussions also revolved around how possible strides towards sustainability might inadvertently place certain groups of researchers, such as early career researchers, at a disadvantage, highlighting the necessity for initiatives to be appraised through an ethical and inclusivity-focused lens.

Promoting **collegiality and collaboration** formed another significant theme. Some teams expressed a desire to foster a more collaborative atmosphere within their respective universities, while others discussed enhancing collaborations across the university sector. The potential to strengthen ties with industry, the public, and third sectors was discussed, along with the need for equitable partnerships informed by knowledge exchange and research collaboration frameworks.

Reflections Following the Lightning Talks

In the discussions following the lightning talks, there was a shared recognition of the imperative for universities to embrace substantial change. Discussions surfaced around the complexities of research culture initiatives, which are often criticised for their fragmented implementation, creating a call for more cohesive approaches. The entrenched resistance to transformation was identified as a considerable barrier, underscoring the sentiment that impactful and meaningful change is not a swift process but one that evolves gradually, often dependent on the efforts of under-resourced and under-recognised teams and individuals. Some teams reflected on the potential positive impact arising from the required involvement of senior university leaders as lead applicants on IFRC bids. Wellcome hopes to continue learning with the community about the impact of IFRC on resourcing, recognition, and institutional commitment to research culture work.

Amidst these reflections, the influence of the Research Excellence Framework (REF) on UK research culture was a focal point of debate. Participants expressed contrasting views: while some saw REF metrics as potentially fostering a competitive rather than a collaborative ethos, others posited that the REF could be leveraged as a potent catalyst for positive change. The constructive role of the REF

was envisioned as promoting openness and collaboration, with the capacity to recognise shared outcomes and encourage open research practices. It was suggested that by drawing attention to and showcasing successful examples, REF could drive a more collective and beneficial research culture.

Further discussions emphasised the necessity of rigorous evaluation to verify the impact of research culture projects. An important caution was raised against viewing these endeavours merely as short-term remedies bolstered by funding. Instead, there was advocacy for long-lasting, financially viable solutions that universities can sustain beyond the initial infusion of resources, embedding these changes into the structural fabric of the institutions.

As well as knowledge sharing between institutions, the lightning talks fulfilled a role requested by attendees to “put a face to a name” and introduce the people behind research culture work at different institutions as a starting point for further interactions.

Facilitated Discussions

In the afternoon, participants reconvened for a series of facilitated discussions focused on topics of shared interest within the community. The topics were preselected based on prior conversations with institutional teams and feedback from a pre-event survey. The array of themes on the table for discussion covered a spectrum of important issues, including reimagining leadership and team dynamics, the evaluation process, acknowledging diverse roles and career paths, shifting from competition to collaboration, and addressing anti-racist practices within research cultures. Appendix 2 provides a list of the discussion topics and how many groups discussed each theme.

In these discussions, participants were asked to explore the following questions:

- What is our focus question?
- What changes do we want to see?
- What actions or initiatives towards change are currently taking place (in this discussion group, this community, and/or the wider sector)?
- What actions in this community could create a new momentum towards change?
- What might be some of the unintended consequences to consider?

Feedback revealed that these dialogues were deeply engaging, sparking vibrant exchanges and uniting attendees over shared concerns and aspirations. Although these discussions were just a starting point, it was encouraging to observe a widespread eagerness to extend these dialogues beyond the event, with many expressing an intention to maintain the momentum. Attendees made notes on their discussions in either paper or digital formats, which the facilitators made available to the community after the event, creating a documentary basis for furthering these discussions.

Reflections from the Survey Feedback

We are hopeful that the kick-off event has sparked numerous opportunities for enhanced collaboration and knowledge exchange between institutions, a sentiment echoed by attendee feedback. Over half of the attendants (53%) engaged in their first cross-institutional dialogue on research culture at this event, highlighting its unique role in facilitating conversations that may otherwise not occur. Many participants (59%) expanded their networks by making new connections or strengthening existing ones, building connections across diverse research entities. With 62% of attendees planning post-event follow-up conversations and 41% offering cross-institutional collaboration, there was a clear drive to transform initial interactions into tangible partnerships.

Furthermore, 90% of attendees reported discovering practices from others' research culture work that they can integrate into their own work, highlighting the event's practical impact through shared insights. The kick-off has sparked communication and collaboration across institutions, with the majority seeking to maintain these valuable connections and leverage newly acquired knowledge. This underscores the event's pivotal role as a platform for supporting ambitious projects, fostering collaboration, and sharing the benefits within the research community, driving collective growth and learning.

Next Steps . . .

This event was the first of many convenings of the IRCC community. Over the coming two years, there will be at least two more large events that will be different in format and location to serve the evolving needs of the community. Additionally, there will be several smaller, more focused gatherings for subsets of the community with specific interests, such as emerging goals, research culture topics, challenges, or connecting individuals in similar roles. To support the community to come together around its evolving aims, Wellcome has commissioned [Studio Susegad](#) (consisting of [Roseanna Dias](#), [Tony Bhajam](#), and [Dr. Furaha Asani](#)), a Bristol-based creative production, research, and consultancy studio focused on rest, care, and connection as embedded social researchers. They will support IRCC's exploration of inclusive research cultures and promote shared collective and joined-up learning between IRCC teams.

Studio Susegad met the community for the first time at the kick-off event, and shared their reflections on the day:

“At the kick-off event, we asked attendees what they wanted the IRCC to feel like, and some responded that they wanted it to be open, not too structured, honest, safe, respectful, and inclusive. As a collective deeply invested in care praxis, we were also interested in finding out what ‘care’ means to the IRCC, how it's embedded within the community itself and the community's work. The responses we got were that care is: “taking time and permission to take time”; “being the change we want to see by being caring, and acting with care”; and also, a concern that “care should mean more than it does”.

Attendees told us that they were hopeful about developing and sharing learnings, linking questions to action, and fostering a space for genuine changemakers and action. They expressed that they're conscious of the IRCC's shared ability to be vulnerable, and aware of hierarchies and REF competition. They're keen for better representation in the room, and slightly worried about the IRCC's collective ability to affect actual change.

A noteworthy point we raised at the end of the event, when we had a chance to address the room directly, was our own awareness of the tensions between wanting to make change whilst existing in an inherently competitive system (academia) that is foregrounded in rigid structures and power dynamics. We also know that the IRCC is truly dedicated to the improvement of research cultures in the UK's research landscape (and even further afield, within its circle of influence).

Over the coming years, Studio Susegad will act as a sounding board and provide a space for solidarity. We will also provide timely updates to promote joined-up thinking and frameworks that get the IRCC thinking about how to implement change based on available capacity, resources, and power. We will also facilitate the storytelling element of the IRCC.

Within the community, we share quarterly newsletters and plan to host hybrid regional events between the first and second quarters of 2025. We will also co-produce the mid-point meeting with the Wellcome team. Alongside sharing learnings within the IRCC, both we and the community are keen to have a structured mechanism for broader dissemination. Therefore, one of our key priorities in 2025 is to create an online presence for the IRCC via a webpage where we can share learnings that are beneficial to the wider sector.

Additionally, every month we host an online session for IRCC members, with two sessions per year being open to the wider sector. These sessions allow participants to come together to explore emerging themes within the research culture landscape. Please reach out to us at hello@irccsusegad.com if you have any questions or would like to start up a conversation."

Acknowledgements

Our thanks go to a large group of teams and individuals who made the launch of Wellcome's Institutional Research Culture Community possible.

Firstly, our thanks go to the heart of the community: its 42 member teams, including those who prepared and gave a lightning talk, and everyone who contributed their ideas, thoughts, feelings, and leadership in discussions.

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Appendix 1

List of organisations invited to IFRC

- Birkbeck University of London
- Cardiff University
- Goldsmiths, University of London
- Imperial College London
- Institute of Cancer Research
- Keele University
- King's College London
- Lancaster University
- Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine
- London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine
- National University of Ireland Galway
- Newcastle University
- Queen Mary University of London
- Queen's University Belfast
- St George's, University of London
- Trinity College Dublin
- University College Cork
- University College Dublin
- University College London
- University of Aberdeen
- University of Birmingham
- University of Bristol
- University of Cambridge
- University of Dundee
- University of Durham
- University of East Anglia
- University of Edinburgh
- University of Exeter
- University of Glasgow
- University of Leeds
- University of Leicester
- University of Liverpool
- University of Manchester
- University of Nottingham
- University of Oxford
- University of Sheffield
- University of Southampton
- University of St Andrews

- University of Strathclyde
- University of Sussex
- University of Warwick
- University of York

Appendix 2

List of facilitated discussion topics

The number of teams that discussed each topic is included in brackets

- Rethinking leadership (3 teams)
- Rethinking teams
- Recognition of all career paths and roles (4 team)
- EDI informed recruitment and promotion (1 team)
- Team composition and intersectionality
- Career development for minoritized researchers (1 team)
- Focus on ableism and anti-ableism in research cultures (1 team)
- Focus on racism, whiteness and anti-racism in research cultures (1 team)
- Focus on class and socioeconomic barriers (2 teams)
- Focus on neuroinclusive cultures
- Evaluation (3 teams)
- Embedding Lived experience perspectives in our work (2 teams)
- Living our own values in projects
- Influencing and advocacy (2 teams)
- Supporting other teams projects (1 team)
- Moving from competition to collaboration (3 teams)
- Creating authentically interdisciplinary spaces (2 teams)
- Fixed-term contracts (2 teams)
- Bullying and harassment (2 teams)
- Supporting PhD/Postgraduate researchers (2 teams)
- Supporting mid-career researchers (2 teams)
- Systems change, link, structures, drivers (2 teams)
- Funding research cultures (2 teams)
- Learning from other sectors (1 team)
- Recognising research professionals (1 team)

DISRUPT

HIERARCHY
AND REMOVE
CYNICISM

LIFTING THE LID ON
WHAT IS HIDDEN
AND OPENING IT

FOR EVERYONE

CHANGE

through
COLLABORATION

JOIN
FORCES FOR
FUNDING
APPLICATIONS

WORKING
WITH A

MULTI PRONGED APPROACH

EMPOWER EDI

SHARE
LEARNINGS

DISABILITY

IS THE
DRIVER
OF
CREATING

INCLUSIVE RESEARCH CULTURES

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

PEER NETWORKS

EMBED COLLEGIALITY

CONTESTING
SYSTEMIC
ABLEISM
IN
INSTITUTIONS

MENTORING

BOOST WELL-BEING

SHARING RESOURCES

WORK WITH RECRUITMENT

REFRAMING LANGUAGE

GETTING POLICIES and PROCEDURES IN PLACE

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